

Correlation between Home-Background and Achievement in Mathematics among Primary School Pupils in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study adopted correlational design to examine correlation between home-background and achievement in mathematics among primary school pupils with Dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research questions were posed and two hypotheses formulated to guide the study. Multiple sampling approaches including purposive sampling approaches, teacher nomination check list, school record was used to select a sample of 130 pupils' with dyscalculia for the study. Two instruments titled "questionnaire Home background" and Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) were developed by the researcher and validated by experts and used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined and the coefficient using Alpha Cronbach Method and Kuder-Richardson formula (21) was found to be 0.82, 0.84 and 0.83 for parental involvement, home learning environment and Mathematics achievement respectively. The hypotheses were tested using Simple Linear Regression for hypotheses for two hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings indicated that both parental involvement and home learning environment were significant predictors of academic achievement, accounting for 16.2% and 20.2% of the variance respectively. It was concluded that fostering a supportive home environment through active parental engagement can support the mathematical skills of pupils with dyscalculia. Recommendations include the creation of conducive learning environments at home and increased parental participation in educational activities, to enhance the academic outcomes for these pupils.

Keywords: Home background, Mathematics achievement, parental involvement, home learning environment.

Introduction

Dyscalculia is a specific learning disability that affects an individual's ability to understand and manipulate numbers or mathematical concepts. It is characterized by difficulties in performing arithmetic operations, understanding numerical relationships, and comprehending mathematical symbols. Dyscalculia can manifest in various ways, including problems with counting, number sense, and mathematical reasoning. It has been observed that individuals with dyscalculia struggle to grasp the concept of quantity and numerical relationships, trouble in understanding and using mathematical symbols and notation, have challenges in performing basic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division which affected their overall academic achievement in Mathematics (Ogar, Ibok, Odey, Joseph, Unimuke, . & Ungie, 2023). A good academic achievement in Mathematics of pupils' with dyscalculia does not happen by chance. It is a product of effective teaching and learning coupled with the effort of the teachers in the school, and parents at their various home background (Fuchs & Fuchs 2017; Fuchs & Fuchs, 2020). Home background refers to the social, economic, and cultural environment in which a child is raised. It encompasses various factors, including family structure, parental education,

socioeconomic status, cultural values, and the availability of resources and support systems. Home background significantly influences a child's development, educational experiences, and overall well-being (Hill & Tyson, 2015; Geary, 2019).

Disparities in achievement result from the majority of parents' lack of resources or expertise to properly assist their kids' arithmetic development. Additionally, parents are not well-versed in how to properly explain mathematics to their children, which can result in misconceptions and a lack of faith in their skills. Some of them lack the necessary skills or confidence to engage meaningfully in their children's mathematical education (Eburu et al. 2023). Many parents are unsure about how to effectively engage in their children's education, particularly in mathematics. Although some parents engage in various supportive practices, including helping with homework, providing resources, and creating a conducive learning environment. However, not all forms of support are equally effective in promoting mathematics achievement of pupils with Dyscalculia. Understanding the mechanisms through which home background influence mathematics achievement is essential. Addressing these factors can help create supportive environments that enhance the academic outcomes for pupils with dyscalculia. (Butterworth & Yeo 2015; Butterworth, & Yeo, 2017). The academic achievement of pupils with dyscalculia is influenced by various home background factors, including parental involvement, home learning environment. These home factors are identified as important factors that determine the academic success of children with learning disabilities, including dyscalculia.

Parental involvement refers to the active participation of parents in their children's education, including involvement in school activities, homework, and creating a supportive home learning environment. Active parental involvement in a child's education significantly influences their academic achievement, particularly in mathematics. When parents engage in homework support, provide encouragement, and participate in math-related activities, it fosters a positive learning environment. This involvement helps pupils with dyscalculia develop better mathematical skills and confidence. Parental involvement can take various forms, including direct academic support, emotional encouragement, and the creation of a conducive learning environment (Kaufmann & von Aster, 2021). Mazzocco (2017) stated that children with dyscalculia benefit significantly from parents who engage in their learning process, providing assistance with homework and participating in math-related activities. This active involvement helps reinforce mathematical concepts and boosts confidence. Jeynes (2016) found a positive relationship between parental involvement and students' academic achievement. A study conducted by Geary (2019) found that when parents express belief in their child's abilities and provide emotional encouragement, it positively impacts the child's attitude towards mathematics. This support can help alleviate anxiety and frustration, common among pupils with dyscalculia, thereby enhancing their academic performance. Davis-Kean, (2019) found a significant influence of parent education in terms of involving on child achievement. Fuchs, and Fuchs, D. (2016) conducted a study of role of family involvement in the mathematics achievement of students with learning disabilities and found parental involvement significantly influence mathematics achievement of students with learning disabilities. Mazzocco and Thompson (2017) conducted a study a study on home factors and mathematics achievement and found a significant influence of parental support on mathematics achievement. Miller and Tinsley (2018) found a significant influence of parental support on the mathematics achievement of students with learning disabilities. Sirin (2018) found a significant influence parental financial support on academic achievement:

Research conducted by Butterworth and Yeo (2015) emphasized the importance of using effective strategies in parental involvement. Parents who utilized structured approaches, such as incorporating games and visual aids into learning, were more successful in helping their children grasp mathematical concepts. This study found that such strategies not only improved understanding but also made learning more enjoyable for children with dyscalculia. Van der Ven et al. (2020) found out that higher socioeconomic status often correlates with greater access to educational resources, which can enhance parental involvement in mathematics. The study indicated that pupils with dyscalculia from higher SES backgrounds tended to perform better academically due to the additional support and resources available at home. A longitudinal study conducted by Ritchie and Bates (2019) demonstrated that sustained parental involvement over time leads to better long-term academic outcomes for children with dyscalculia. The study concluded that consistent engagement in a child's education fosters a strong foundation in mathematical skills, helping to close the achievement gap between pupils with dyscalculia and their peers. Parental involvement and engagement in children's education—such as helping with homework and encouraging mathematical discussions, the quality of the home learning environment, including access to educational resources (such as books, manipulative, and technology), can improve academic performance (Hill & Tyson, 2015; Fan & Chen, 2019). Conclusively, active engagement, emotional support, effective strategies, and socioeconomic factors contributed to the level of parental involvement and its impact on mathematical performance.

The quality of the home learning environment, including access to educational resources (such as books, manipulative, and technology), plays a crucial role in shaping a child's mathematical abilities. A stimulating environment that encourages exploration and practice can help mitigate the challenges faced by pupils with dyscalculia, leading to improved academic outcomes in mathematics. By fostering a supportive and engaging home environment, parents can significantly enhance their children's learning experiences and outcomes in mathematics. The home learning environment (HLE) plays a crucial role in the academic achievement of children, particularly those with learning disabilities like dyscalculia. For instance, a study conducted by O'Connor et al. (2020) found that parents who actively participated in their children's learning, particularly in mathematics, positively influenced their children's academic achievement. Research conducted by Landerl et al. (2018) found that children exposed to a variety of mathematical resources at home perform better in mathematics. Access to educational materials, such as books, games, and technology, is crucial for children with dyscalculia. Additionally, a meta-analysis conducted by McGough et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of using manipulative and digital tools to support the learning of children with dyscalculia. According to a study by Kearney et al. (2022), children with dyscalculia who experienced a supportive home environment showed improved attitudes towards mathematics, which in turn enhanced their academic performance. A positive and encouraging learning atmosphere at home can reduce anxiety and foster a love for learning. Kearney, Albano and McGuire (2022) examine the role of family support in the academic achievement of children with learning disabilities and found home environment significant on the academic achievement of pupils with learning disabilities.

Kauffman and Landrum (2019) found a significant influence of home environment on the academic success of students with dyscalculia. Research conducted by Kauffman, Landrum, and McGhee (2019) found that pupils with dyscalculia who came from homes with rich mathematical interactions performed better in standardized math assessments compared to those from less supportive environments. Sullivan, and Brown (2020) found home learning environment significantly influence mathematics achievement in children with dyscalculia. Ritchie and Bates (2019) conducted a study indicating that a rich home learning environment—characterized by access to books, educational games, and parental encouragement—positively correlates with improved mathematical skills among children with dyscalculia. The study emphasizes that a stimulating environment can help mitigate some of the difficulties faced by these pupils. A longitudinal study by Bock et al. (2021) demonstrated that early interventions in the home learning environment, such as introducing math-related activities, led to significant improvements in mathematical skills over time. Fuchs et al. (2020) stated that the importance of structured home-based interventions that focus on mathematical skills, lead to improved outcomes for children with dyscalculia. Parental involvement, access to educational resources, and a supportive learning atmosphere are critical factors that can enhance mathematical understanding and performance. Pupils with dyscalculia who had access to tailored educational resources—such as apps designed for learning math—showed significant improvement in their mathematical abilities. A stimulating and supportive home environment that encourages learning can help children with dyscalculia develop better coping strategies and skills in mathematics.

Research questions

The following research questions were posed

1. How does parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?
2. How does home learning environment relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant relationship between Parental involvement and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant relationship between Learning Environment and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study area was Mbo Local Government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The research design used for this study was the correlational survey design. The researchers used this design to established the relationship between home background variables (in terms parental involvement and home learning environment) and academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics . The population for the study consists of all the 330 primary four pupils' with dyscalculia in 25 public primary schools in Mbo Local Government area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Multi stage sampling procedure was adopted for the study which consisted From the each selected schools, researchers used school Mathematics

Record and Teacher Nomination Checklist to select a sample of 130 pupils' with dyscalculia for the study. The instruments used for data collection were the questionnaire titled "Home background and achievement test in Mathematics. The questionnaire was made of 12 items, with 6 items to measure each sub-level in terms of parental involvement and home learning environment.. The questionnaire was based on four point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Mathematics Achievement Test was made up of 25 items constructed by the researchers with help of two experts in Mathematics education. The items were constructed based on primary four Mathematics syllabus with four options A, B, C, D. A correct answer attracts one mark while incorrect answer attracts zero (0)mark. The instrument was face-validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation, two expert in special educators and two Mathematics Educators, all from the University of Calabar. Corrections were pointed out by the experts and adjusted by the researchers and the document was considered valid. The reliability of the questionnaire using Alpha Cronbach Method for .82 for parental involvement and .84 for home learning environment while the reliability estimate of the pupils' Mathematics achievement test was established through Kuder Richardson formula K-R20 which gives .83. Since the reliability index is above 0.50, the estimates were considered high enough for the study. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) computer programme was used to analyze the data collected. The hypotheses were tested using Simple Linear Regression for two hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at -05 level of significance.

Presentation of results

The result of the analysis is presented in tables 1, 2, 3 and 4. Descriptive statistics was used to answer research questions while Simple regression Analysis was used to test the null hypotheses at .05 significant level.

Research question one

How does parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia? The research question was answered using co-efficient of determinant. This was based on the data generated from responses to the questionnaire items on parental involvement as it relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The result is presented in 1.

Table1: Beta(B) and adjusted R² on the how parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?

Variable	B	SE	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Parental involvement	.675	3.87654	.164	.162

Sources; Fieldwork, 2024

The result in Table 1 shows the extent to which parental involvement relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with adjusted r-square of .162. This indicated that parental involvement accounted for 16.2%, which is low determinants of academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria Also, the Beta value of .675 which measuring the effect size or the strength of a relationship between variables showing that parental involvement contributed 67.5% effect which is moderate on achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria

Research question two

How does home learning environment relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia? The research question was answered using co-efficient of determinant. This was based on the data generated from responses to the questionnaire items on home learning environment as its relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The result is presented in 2.

Table 2: Beta (B) and adjusted R² on the how home learning environment relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia?

Variable	B	SE	R ²	Adjusted R ²
Home learning environment	.786	3.76548	.204	.202

Sources: Field work 2024

The result in Table 2 shows the extent to which home learning relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with adjusted r-square of .202. This indicated that home learning environment accounted for 20.2%, which is low determinants of academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa

Ibom state, Nigeria Also, the Beta value of .786 which measuring the effect size or the strength of a relationship between variables showing that home learning environment contributed 78. 6 % effect which is high on achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria

Testing the null hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Parental involvement and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo local government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

The independent variable in this hypothesis is parental involvement while the dependent variable is achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. To test this hypothesis, Simple Linear regression was used. The F-ratio test was used to test for the significance of the overall prediction model, r-value was used to established the relationship between the variables while t-test was used to test for the significance of the contribution of the regression constant and coefficient (which represents the predictive power of the independent variable) in the prediction model. The mean and standard deviation of the variables were also computed as it is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis of Parental involvement as it relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia

Variables	X		SD		
Parental involvement	15.987		1.7654		
Mathematics achievement	18.908		2.8765		
R-value = .405			Adjusted R-squared = .162		
R-squared = .164			Standard error = 3.87654		
Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	P-value
Regression	654.908	1	654.908	25.151	.000*
Residual	3332.989	128	26.039		
Total	3987.897	129			
Predictor variable	Unstandardized coefficient B	Std.error	Std.coeff	t-value	p-value
Constant	34.897	3.196		10.919*	.000
Parental involvement	.675	.123	.096	5.488*	.000

Significant at .05 level. P<.05

The results in Table 3 show that the R-value of .405 was obtained which shows a positive low relationship between Parental involvement and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The R value resulting in an R-squared value of .164 and adjusted R-square value of 162. This means that the variation of parental involvement accounted for about only 16.2% of the total variation in achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The p-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (25.151) was less than .05. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that Parental involvement significantly influence achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with both the regression constant (34.874) and coefficient (.675) contributing significantly in the prediction model (t= 10.919 & 5.488 respectively, p=.000 & .000 < .05).

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between Learning Environment and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia in Mbo Local Government, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is home learning environment while the dependent variable is achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. To test this hypothesis, Simple Linear regression was used. The F-ratio test was used to test for the significance of the overall prediction model, r-value was used to established the relationship between the variables while t-test was used to test for the significance of the contribution of the regression constant and coefficient (which represents the predictive power of the independent variable) in the prediction model. The mean and standard deviation of the variables were also computed as it is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Simple Regression Analysis of home learning environment as it relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia

Variables	X	SD			
Home learning environment	14.543	1.6542			
Mathematics achievement	18.908	2.8765			
R-value = .452		Adjusted R-squared = .202			
R-squared = .204		Standard error = 3.76548			
Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	P-value
Regression	813.763	1	813.763	32.816	.000*
Residual	3174.134	128	24.798		
Total	3987.897	129			
Predictor variable	Unstandardized coefficient B	Std.error	Std.coeff	t-value	p-value
Constant	37.986	2.987		12.717*	.000
Home environment	.786	.162	.121	4.852*	.000

Significant at .05 level. $P < .05$

The results in Table 4 show that the R-value of .452 was obtained which shows a positive low relationship between home learning environment and achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia. The R value resulting in an R-squared value of .204 and adjusted R-square value of .202. This means that the variation of home learning environment accounted for about only 20.2% of the total variation in academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics. The p-value (.000) associated with the computed F-value (32,816) was less than .05. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that home learning environment significantly influence achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia with both the regression constant (37.986) and coefficient (.786) contributing significantly in the prediction model ($t = 12.717$ & 4.852 respectively, $p = .000$ & $.000 < .05$).

Discussion of finding

The result of the first hypothesis revealed that parental involvement significantly predicts academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics. The finding agreed with Mazzocco (2017) who stated that children with dyscalculia benefit significantly from parents who engage in their learning process, providing assistance with homework and participating in math-related activities. This active involvement helps reinforce mathematical concepts and boosts confidence. The finding is in line with a study conducted by Geary (2019) who found that when parents express belief in their child's abilities and provide emotional encouragement, it positively impacts the child's attitude towards mathematics. According to Butterworth and Yeo (2015), parents who utilized structured approaches, such as incorporating games and visual aids into learning, were more successful in helping their children grasp mathematical concepts. This study found that such strategies not only improved understanding but also made learning more enjoyable for children with dyscalculia. The finding is in line with Van der Ven et al. (2020) found out that higher socioeconomic status often correlates with greater access to educational resources, which can enhance parental involvement in mathematics. The finding agreed with a longitudinal study conducted by Ritchie and Bates (2019) who stated that sustained parental involvement over time leads to better long-term academic outcomes for children with dyscalculia. The study concluded that consistent engagement in a child's education fosters a strong foundation in mathematical skills, helping to close the achievement gap between pupils with dyscalculia and their peers.

The result of the second hypothesis revealed that home learning environment significantly predicts academic achievement of pupils' with dyscalculia in Mathematics. The finding agreed a study conducted by O'Connor et al. (2020) who found that parents who actively participated in their children's learning, particularly in mathematics, positively influenced their children's academic achievement. The finding is in line with a research conducted by Landerl et al. (2018) who found that children exposed to a variety of mathematical resources at home perform better in mathematics. According to a study by Kearney et al. (2022), children with dyscalculia who experienced a supportive home environment showed improved attitudes towards mathematics, which in turn enhanced their academic performance. A positive and encouraging learning atmosphere at

home can reduce anxiety and foster a love for learning. The finding is in consonance with a research conducted by Kauffman et al. (2019) who found that pupils with dyscalculia who came from homes with rich mathematical interactions performed better in standardized math assessments compared to those from less supportive environments. The finding agreed with Ritchie and Bates (2019) and found home learning environment—characterized by access to books, educational games, and parental encouragement positively correlates with improved mathematical skills among children with dyscalculia. The finding agreed with Bock et al. (2021) who found that home learning environment, such as introducing math-related activities, led to significant improvements in mathematical skills over time.

Conclusion

The development of mathematics skills in children with dyscalculia is significantly influenced by various home factors, including parental involvement and the overall home learning environment. Pupils with dyscalculia who receive active engagement and support from their parents tend to perform better in mathematics. A nurturing home environment that encourages learning, provides resources, and fosters positive attitudes towards mathematics can mitigate some of the challenges faced by children with dyscalculia. Parental involvement home learning environment not only enhances academic achievement but also contributes to the emotional and psychological well-being of these children. Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that parental involvement, home learning environment significant relate with achievement in mathematics among pupils with dyscalculia.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommended were made

1. Schools should encourage parents to participate in their children's education actively. Workshops and seminar should be organized regularly for parents to equip parents with strategies to support their children's learning effectively.
2. Parents should create a conducive learning space at home that is free from distractions and equipped with necessary learning materials. This environment would promote curiosity and exploration of mathematical concepts.
3. Schools and educational organizations should provide parents with access to resources, such as educational games, apps, and books tailored for children with dyscalculia. These tools can help to reinforce learning outside the classroom.
4. Establishing regular communication between parents and teachers is recommended to help track the child's progress and address any challenges promptly. This collaboration can lead to more tailored support for the child.
5. Schools should develop specialized programs that focus on enhancing parental support and involvement for children with dyscalculia. These programs should include individualized learning plans that involve parents in the educational process.

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